

EDITORIALS

Editorial

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E koekoe te tūi, e ketekete te kākā, e kūkū te kererū,
The tūi squawks, the kākā chatters, the kererū coos.
(It takes all kinds of people).

Tēnā tātou katoa

We're delighted to introduce this latest edition of the Journal, which has a special focus on clinical psychology practice with Aroreretini/Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) in Aotearoa New Zealand. Thanks to all of our authors and reviewers for their help with this edition, which includes some very thought-provoking content.

As the above whakataukī suggests, diversity is something that we try to celebrate as a profession- with respect for the dignity of persons and peoples, together with the Treaty of Waitangi, central to our current Code of Ethics (2012). In addition to articles on ADHD, this issue also includes research by Dr Kyle Tan and his colleagues from Waikato University, highlighting the poor record of psychology journals in New Zealand, including our own, on including content that represents the diversity of the people of Aotearoa. As an editorial team, this is something that we are extremely mindful of and have been working hard to improve. In that respect, we're pleased to also include articles by Kyle Tan, Charlotte Almao & Julia Ioane, and Diana Kopua with a focus on Asian people, Pasifika communities and Māori respectively, as well as the perspective of a person with lived experience of ADHD provided by Hannah Hardy-Jones. We're also pleased to see that so many of our authors have taken care to consider wider aspects of diversity- including our Treaty of Waitangi commitments- as part of their submissions.

We would also like to acknowledge that the Journal has a new format, having moved to a new platform provided by Scholastica. This is a big step forward for the Journal as a showcase for the work of our profession, making all of our articles fully indexed in Google and Google Scholar and significantly improving their visibility online.

We are delighted to announce that our next issue, planned for publication in the Summer, will focus on Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing Therapy and will be guest edited by accredited EMDR trainers Dr Tal Moore and Dr Tom Flewett. A call for papers for the next issue will go out to NZCCP members in the next few weeks.

Ngā mihi nui ki a koutou.
Paul (Guest Editor)
Liesje & Wade (Permanent Editors)